

CORRUPTION IS THE BIGGEST CRIME, BETRAYAL OF THE STATE

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Abstract: *In this article we will talk about the fact that corruption is the biggest crime, a scam to the state. The author relied on legal knowledge, analyzed the problem on the basis of existing legal literature and studied the existing peculiarities of the role and importance of modern techniques in the teaching of languages.*

Keywords: *corruption, state, society, laws, crime.*

It is known that as society progresses, laws also develop. Each country has its own law. The most sad thing is that some people try to justify themselves as if they were released to break the law. For example, an offender is detained and punished without violating the law, but he violates another law, as a result of which he also offers illegal money to the defender of the law to get rid of this punishment. We are talking about bribery, that is, corruption, in this article!. Corruption civil society is a worm that eats its tree.

As the saying goes about corruption, it is a terrible illusion that society can be reigned in different ways. Corruption hinders the rise of the country, the development of democracy. As a result, the people begin to lag behind. They cause a mood that subordinates the human mind to indifference, immortality.

A person becomes indifferent to him without seeing that his rights and freedoms, duties are violated. As a result, it can not affect the environment itself. At a time when democracy and human rights are being undermined, the fact that members of society do not have a position to do so does not feed the country from the inside. When will the state rise to the highest peak in development, when will it be able to join the ranks of Democratic states? Does not it depend on the legal consciousness of citizens? If a citizen does not know the law and does not follow it, what will be his contribution to the development of society? Why does the law not apply to it knowingly? These questions still make us think. It's time to continue. We need to start an effort to get rid of corruption from our own society.

They approach the term corruption in the world in different ways, namely-corruption is the aspiration of state power for personal benefit. According to the authors of the legal encyclopedia – corruption is a policy or criminal activity in the field of Public Administration, expressed in the use of the rights and opportunities of power granted to them by officials to acquire personal wealth,-explains. In fact, corruption is only among state officials! I think not! this is a high view of the corruption they portray. From an etymological point of view-the term corruption comes from the Latin word corruptio, which means a violation, a deviation from the Bokonyi monetary evasion. So, from this it is possible to know that any non-monetary evasion is a case of corruption.

The abuse of office by officials to influence others through the use of their position has made corruption a convenient way to accomplish its goal more quickly. An official can easily achieve his goal without unnecessary difficulties, efforts or help someone through this. The person who received help as a result is also grateful to the one who helped. People easily employ their niece or others in an enterprise or firm by using their position. But the nephew is not worth it, he does not even know how to behave. In the end, try to imagine the situation in which he is an enterprise. The head, who does not know how to conduct business, degrades the enterprise. If this situation is in the state bodies, law and other various careers? Oh, yeah! Right now the state will go according to the recession.

In the fight against corruption, law enforcement agencies should not act in an arbitrary way, unless our people are uncompromising this disgusting evil, establish impressive public control, we can not organize an effective struggle against this scourge.

It is a pity, of course, that the positive attitude towards corruption among citizens, that is, instead of condemning corruption as a whole, causes it to take a deeper root in our society. It is only a crime to condemn corruption in front of others, but to abuse one's position without observance of what has been said, opinions, to act contrary to the law and to give it up, to associate someone in this matter with himself, but people, according to them, repeat and repeat these actions. But corruption is not allowed in a society brought up in a democratic spirit. So it is necessary to educate citizens in a democratic spirit. From this it follows that education should be started first of all from ourselves, that is, from young people. Each person must spend the day with his labor, achieve success in the evasion of his labor, always be impartial in the performance of his work and act in accordance with the law.

The world's prominent countries are also struggling against the Bribery Act. For example, the famous phrase that the leader of the state of Singapore, Lee Kuan Yu, says that a person who wants to win over corruption should be ready to imprison both his relatives and close friends is an indication that the fight against corruption in the country is unprofitable.

If a corrupt official in Singapore received a prison sentence for a certain period of time, China introduced a life sentence or a death penalty for this. According to information, since 2003 year in this state about 10 thousand officials have been sentenced to shot, 120 thousand of them have been imprisoned for a long time.

In some cases, the hands of officials detained with illegal money are chapped. In addition, the Chinese participate in special courses on the fight against illegal money laundering. Civil servants heal the mind and body through mental and physical exercises. Also in China, an online game has already been developed, in which users will have to scrape the corrupt officials with all their relatives.

Hong Kong, which is located next to China, is also worth praising its success in the fight against corruption – previously almost all government agencies of the country were immersed in the swamp of corruption. To get out of this swamp, the following measures were taken: it is necessary to prove that state officials bought at their own expense all the goods, cars and other valuables that they honestly found. If he can not prove it, the prison will wait for him and all his property will be confiscated. Secondly, here in 1974 year-an independent Anti-Corruption Commission was formed, consisting of officers, intellectuals and businessmen. They receive a very large salary and are subject only to the governor. Finally, he said Hong Kong residents and media representatives were given ample opportunities to fight bribery – citizens could complain to the commission over the officer who asked for pora, while journalists could investigate the activities of any officer. And the result is amazing – in 30 years the level of bribery fell from 90 percent to 3 percent.

The first president of our country Islam Karimov, at the dawn of the 21st century of Uzbekistan: in the work of security threats, conditions of stability and guarantees of progress, talked about corruption and bribery, – the escalation of crime and corruption did not eat up the constitutional foundations of the state, causing serious violations of the rights and freedoms of citizens. – It is argued that the absolutely naughty rule that the purpose of adopting laws and decrees is to circumvent them, leads to the

deprivation of the ability of society to maintain the simplest legal order and public order.

Let's look at what reforms are being carried out in Uzbekistan in the fight against corruption: Uzbekistan joined the UN Convention on the fight against corruption on July 7, 2008, the Istanbul Plan for the fight against corruption, adopted within the framework of the organization for Economic Cooperation and development in March 2010 (September 10, 2003). Also, the Supreme Assembly ratified the agreement on the Eurasian Group on combating legalization of income and financing of terrorism (Moscow, June 16, 2011) on December 13, 2011.

The law on Combating Corruption came into force in Uzbekistan from 4th January 2017.

In accordance with the resolution of the Republic of Uzbekistan of the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Combating Corruption was adopted by the legislative chamber on 24 November 2016 and approved by the Senate on 13 December 2016 and approved by the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev. 2017-th year came into force from 4-th year. Control over the execution of this decision the Prime Minister of the Republic of Uzbekistan A.N.Aripov and the Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.B.Abdullaev was charged. This law is an expression from Chapter 6 and Article 34.

According to the law, the Prosecutor General's office, the State Security Service, the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the Ministry of Justice, the Department for combating taxes, currency crimes and the legalization of criminal incomes under the Prosecutor General's office carry out activities to combat corruption in the Republic.

The state program on combating corruption in 2019-2020 and the updated composition of the Republican interdepartmental Commission on combating corruption are intended to be approved. It is envisaged that the bodies of state power and Administration, Public Associations and other organizations will work out effective indicators and agree with the interagency Commission in achieving the objectives of each item of the state program within two months.

In order to coordinate the activities of anti-corruption bodies and organizations participating in it, the Republican interdepartmental Commission on Combating Corruption is obliged to impose a fine of 50 to 100 times the minimum monthly wage or imprisonment for up to 5 years with deprivation of a certain right. When this crime is committed in aggravating circumstances, a prison sentence of 10 to 15 years is appointed.

Respect for laws is formed on the basis of the legal consciousness and culture of our people. That is, if some people are afraid of punishment and obey the law, others respect the law according to the upbringing they received in childhood.

The fight against corruption is not only the duty of responsible employees, or the idea that the heads of state are responsible for this will not be correct at all, but that in the process we can achieve the desired result if we all act as one. Today, great attention is paid to openness in the fight against corruption. In this work that is being done, however, the importance of the mass media is enormous. Many programs that are broadcast on television are conducted based on live and open communication.

The rights and freedoms of journalists were further strengthened. If there is a rule of law in the state, the state will rise. From history it is known that our grandfather Amir Temur, as they say: – in power-in Justice. And a solid and fair society does not flow into progress. Today, we can achieve positive results only if we focus on each sphere and fix the shortcomings in it, radically reform this sphere. One of our greatest efforts in the development of our country and the construction of civil society is the struggle of our citizens against corruption.

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